

Resistant: B1757d-Sm-6-1, B1757d-Sm-47-1, B1757d-Sm-47-3, B1757d-Sm-47-6, B1757d-Sm-50-6, B2012d-SM-52-1-2, BR51-26-10, BRS1-95-2, BR51-196-2, BR52-85-7, IET4154 (CR44-121-1), IET4834 (CR117-1), IET 5126 (RP661-12-4-4-2), IR20, IR532-1-18(S), IR203.5-244-3-2-3,

IR2053-200-4, IR2070-132-2-2-5, IR2070-747-6-3-2-1 (IR32), IR2071-588-4-4, IR2071-803-5-2-6, IR2071-843-1-1-6, IR2328-198-1-1-1, IR2793-97-3-2, IR2798-115-2-3, IR2817-117-2-1, IR2832-172-6-2, OR4422-98-3-6, IR4531-10057-5-1-1, IR4531-10057-5-1-2, A 15-100-1-3-1,

ARC 10618, ARC 10836, DA 29, IR2071-648-4-4-6, IR3464-149-3-2, IR4641-143-1, Nizersail, Rajasail, Tabend, Ta-poo-cho-z, ARC 14342, ARC 14529, ARC 10572, TKM6, and Kattichamba. ■

Donors of bacterial blight resistance

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In 1978 kharif we screened 885 lines from our germplasm collection for bacterial blight resistance at the Kapurthala station. Ten plants of each line were inoculated with a pure culture of *Xanthomonas oryzae* by the clipping method, and scored 15 days later. Seventeen lines were found resistant (score of 3 on the Standard Evaluation

Distribution of scores of resistance donors of bacterial blight inoculated artificially at the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

Score ^a	Leaf area infested (%)	Collections	
		No.	%
1	1	0	0.0
3	1-5	17	1.9
5	5-25	360	40.7
7	25-50	456	51.5
9	50	52	5.9

^aStandard Evaluation System scale.

System scale): Norin 18, Hokkaido, Tainan 3, Taichung 65, IR878B-45-1, IR9880, IR1712-166-1, IR1634-520-1-2, IR1614-605-3-4, Zinnya 31, CK10-152, Norin 18-LC-5, OR45-61-23, A/R-248,

CP231, Chung-Lin-Chun, and Kachamota. Those lines are being used as resistance donors in the breeding program.

Of the others, 360 were scored 5; 456, 7; and 52, 9 (see table). ■

Suggested revision of scoring system for rice sheath rot disease

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Many commercial varieties in the intensive rice-growing areas of India, especially in the rabi or late kharif crop, are susceptible to sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. To incorporate a high degree of resistance into high-yielding varieties, scientists need a systematic approach with a standard scale to screen germplasm and determine resistant genotypes.

The Standard Evaluation System designed by IRRI does not adequately identify resistant donors because the scale is based on the percentage of tillers affected. That gives insufficient information on resistance or susceptibility because if all tillers in a clump are infected to a low degree, we grade that genotype as "9" — regardless of panicle damage. Furthermore, the percentage of affected tillers shows the prevalence of the disease — not its severity.

A scale showing the coverage of lesions on the sheath and their effect on the emerging panicle would more

appropriately identify the resistant lines.

We suggest the scale given in the figure. ■